

Accommodation Engineering in Geriatrics, Bed-Wheelchairs, the promise of freedom.

Dr Bheemaiah, Anil Kumar, A.B Seattle W.A 98125
miyawaki@yopmail.com

Abstract:

We present geriatric bed-wheelchairs as the promise of the freedom, the aged and disabled crave for, finally with the promise of self sufficiency beyond a stigma, and the independence of power assisted living, we explore a farmer soldier story of ardupilot based automation of such a bed-wheelchair with an Alexa VUI.

We explore the applicability of true ergonomics in human computer interfaces in robotic bed chair solutions and autonomous personal mobility, for the slug centered soul. Laziness is indeed proven to be the mother of invention.

Keywords: farmer soldier stories, AWS, Amazon Alexa, Fire TV, Echo Show, Robotic Furniture, Personal Mobility.

What:

Remote patient monitoring and patient infotainment systems with Echo Show and fire stick, and personal mobility with bed-wheelchairs or robotic bed chair furniture for geriatric and generic use case scenarios. Armchair shopping through VUI, proves self sufficiency of children and the aged and disabled needing assistive living.

How:

Accommodation Engineering with VUI, using off the shelf solutions, including inexpensive hardware like the Echo Show and Fire Stick and robotic furniture and bed-wheelchairs.

Why:

Assistive living has always been criticized as lacking in freedom, and constrained, leading to the promise of a technological revolution for freedom, this very freedom is promised in digital medicine, with accommodation engineering, armchair shopping and remote care, all developed from NASA's own space medicine solutions to astronaut wellness. This technology is now offered with an integration of services, by the wellness R&D, Vayu Vaidya.

Introduction.

Automation proves personal care possible without robotics, as accommodation engineering in every case, geriatric and differently abled, making the costs of accommodation negligible with a uniform

experience, to all genres of patients and normal consumers alike. In this paper we present accommodation engineering and powered living as a lifestyle for both normal customers and the aged and disabled, needing assistive living. The promise of independent living with powered

accommodation is possible by the ease of use of technology, all available off the shelf.

Problem Definition.

(Plush Wheelchair Bed - Fully Tilt and Reclining, n.d.)

1. Use of Echo Show combined with a HDMI monitor and the Fire Stick TV for cost effective patient infotainment systems with remote patient monitoring.
2. Use of bed-wheelchair for power assisted independent living with macro stick capture and ardupilot based limited autonomous adaptability.
3. Use of Alexa VUI for a shopping experience from the echo show based infotainment system.

Background.

A case study is presented of a south asian Indian, male aged 94, in need of indoor mobility solutions, and assistance through powered living and personal accommodation engineering. Given the disability in mobility, sit stand and basic skills including personal grooming, foraging and other skills, complete applicability of the above mentioned problem with solutions in robotic furniture or bed-wheel chairs with remote patient monitoring and the use of

voice UI based shopping is presented as a case study, with the use of AWS based, Amazon hardware, including the echo show and the fire stick and a host of patient management digital medicine systems, available as Alexa Skills and integrated AWS based solutions.

Competitive Landscape

(Panasonic's Robotic Bed/wheelchair First to Earn Global Safety Certification, 2014)(SAGE Journals: Your Gateway to World-Class Research Journals, n.d.)(Geri Chairs, n.d.)

Robotic bed chairs and reconfigurable furniture have been available since decades for all genre of users, for personal mobility and ease of daily living.

“This new nursing care robot combines an electric nursing bed and an electric fully reclining wheelchair. Part of the bed changes shape and becomes a wheelchair as it is, so it is possible for even one caregiver to assist a care recipient with moving easily, and recipients in serious condition can be moved in a lying position. It dramatically reduces mental and physical burdens on both caregivers and recipients, and contributes to improvement of recipients' quality of life with more opportunities to get out of bed.”*(Rise Assisting Robot [Panasonic Resyone Plus XPN-S10601], n.d.)*

*(Avera eCARE Senior Care, n.d., Extending Care Delivery Position Paper, n.d.; Evans et al., 2016)*oring and integrated telemedicine solutions abound

(Avera eCARE Senior Care, n.d., Extending Care Delivery Position Paper, n.d.; Evans et al., 2016). The solutions in this paper help market Amazon products as the adoption of ubiquitous A.I towards geriatric care, are cost efficient in reuse of technology and offer better digital medicine than current professional offerings and can be readily integrated into professional services. In the future we prove cost effective and discrimination free, uniform

solutions with the present ubiquitous cloud based AlaaS solutions with Google, Azure and AWS for integrated digital medicine inspired by NASA's space medicine. This is the prime research direction of Vayu Vaidya.

Solution Description

Solution Impact, Scale, and Validation

The experiment consists of using Panasonic reconfigurable bed mobility solutions with 100 geriatric and 100 normal patients coupled with ubiquitous A.I solutions by Amazon, as previously described to create public datasets for medical research. Data is collected using IoT with the panasonic hardware and from direct data collection using ubiquitous sensor integration. The data collected would supplement existing datasets in ergonomics for pre programming ergonomics and automated care providing, towards self sufficiency. The prime research is in the easy usability of the technologies with VUI/BCI or research on total autonomy of care provision with power assistance without patient intervention, using data mining for prediction. Given public datasets and specific datasets for each geriatric case, we predict path planning problems based on well worked out habit planning of patients, thus predicting the daily schedule with access to daily living solutions without much mobility.

The specific data mining solutions are:

1. Sleep pattern detection for patient schedule prediction, coupled with preprogrammed path planning with remote monitoring.
2. Use of presently developed wearable technology based patient monitoring.
3. Use of ubiquitous A.I and VUI for Infotainment.

4. Integration of the smart bed into the smart home for all customers, a smart home market with a sizable equity.

AI Business Case

Explain how you will leverage Artificial Intelligence and machine learning tools and Azure services to address the problem. If the problem can be solved without AI, clarify why AI is critical to your success.

The smart bed is a potential solution to many medical mobility and caregiving solutions, not restricted to medical devices markets, but extensible to smart home solutions, a growing home automation segment. The smart bed is easily integrated into the present smart home and IoT solutions with BLE and WiFi integrations. The present ubiquitous A.I with uniform FaaS, with Azure functions or AWS lambdas allows for the integration of both the Fire TV and Echo Show or any computing with Azure. The addition of the event API and Cognitive API allows for third party skills to be integrated and the presence of third party solutions in addition to biomedical and smart home vendor specific applications.

Description of machine learning model(s) to be generated

A.I for personalized geriatric care and medicine. (*[No Title]*, n.d.)

Study on the importance of self reliance, independence and sufficiency of power assistance with added remote monitoring. Data collection on importance and the nature of the market for power assistance for independent living.

Sleep cycle and daily routines prediction with data mining and IoT with smart bed and use of off the shelf smart home products. Use of Azure Quantum Cloud.

List of the Project Deliverables

- Smart bed IoT design for sleep pattern identification.
- Integration of professional patient monitoring to ubiquitous A.I
- Integration of a smart bed to current Amazon and Microsoft smart home offerings.
- Questionnaire based data collection on independent living by elderly population, using power assistance and role of A.I in geriatrics.
- **prepare self determined individuals able to advocate their wishes, goals, needs, and accommodations in the context of geriatric accommodation engineering.**

Deliverable Information

- Sleep monitoring with IoT and azure for sleep cycle management and posture identification for path planning and daily routine planning. This is to be an application developed on Cortana/Alexa VUI for task planning to help in geriatric accommodations.
- Integration of professional third party patient monitoring and doctor on demand with personal assistance if required, with the echo show and fire TV for integrated patient monitoring using ubiquitous A.I as a product and service offering.
- Product offering of smart bed integration to current Amazon and Microsoft smart home products.
- Research publication in pubmed and psychaXiv on a clinical study on power assisted independent living and the market for independent living products. Research is conducted on accommodation required by self-directed individuals. Product

offering of VUI skills to tailor accommodation towards their wishes, goals and needs, which are identified and quantified to metrics for geriatric accommodation.

Deliverable Data and Data Mining.

Sleep monitoring with IoT and azure for sleep cycle management and posture identification for path planning and daily routine planning. This is to be an application developed on Cortana/Alexa VUI for task planning to help in geriatric accommodations.

The Wyze smart band offers sleep management, physical activity management and general health management functionality in conjunction with leading mobile apps, like Google Fit and Samsung Health. Further data integrated with these apps is collected from the Resyone Mobility device in creating Sleep Habit pattern automation, this data is to be a published data set towards sleep pattern studies with demographic indicators over large populations.

Discussion.

Robotic bed-chair furniture and powered bed-wheelchairs offer macro storage of repeated navigation, thus providing indoor mobility solutions to the aged and disabled, minus the stigma, robotic furniture offers similar mobility solutions to all ages, with the theme, laziness is the mother of invention. Given this right to sluggishness, accommodation engineering takes the form of robotic furniture based mobility and complete automation of personal hygiene and food sourcing.

The need for remote patient monitoring duals with the infotainment of the echo show and the fire stick, providing access to Amazon Prime entertainment and access to

Infotainment and medical information through AWS digital medicine services, integrated are comprehensive pharmaceuticals and online shopping experiences from the armchair. Telemedicine that offers 24/7 medical care, to both normal and the aged and disabled. This accommodation engineering is now available to all genres of consumers, applicable directly to the above mentioned case study of a senior citizen needing mobility and personal assistance.

D.O.E

We test the use of powered bed-wheel chairs for independent mobility in a test set of 100 patients compared with the use of an identical robotic furniture in functionality by a control group of 100 subjects, with data collection on the cloud from the accommodation hardware. Parameters include, ease of use, the usability of the embedded A.I and the difficulty and effort in training and path programming, for personal mobility and ease of use of VUI vs BCI solutions using standard headsets such as MUSE and neurosky.

Wide area camera coverage using the Echo Show for remote medical monitoring allows for video streaming of data to the AWS cloud for further data mining.

Data is also collected from the 100 subjects and the control group on the use of the Fire TV and Echo Show for medical infotainment and patient medical information.

Future Work.

Future work involves the need for Wilderness Therapy in association to outdoor mobility and dual technology, a

return to the elements, proven to have immense wellness benefits to all genres. Marketing in words of silence, proves that OBT and associated therapies, have a preventive medicine and invaluable contribution to wellness, with several testimonies, beyond known scientific explanations of phenomenology of medical effects.

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